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Christianisation of Africa and its effects on the local environmental management : The Case from Ghana¹

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Abstract

Of all the experiences that Africa has gone through, the one that has largely impacted on her life, especially her culture is the Christianisation of the continent which was the direct result of colonialism. This paper investigates indigenous Ghanaians life ways encounter with colonialism and its key appendage, Christianity and the impact of the encounter on the people especially, on their ecological knowledge and practices. Before the advent of Christianity in Ghana in 1482, ecological practices were hugely helped by the indigenous religion, where entities such as rivers, certain species of trees and animals were ascribed with sacred and reverential status were left pristine. The Christian missionaries and their African Christians converts viewed these beliefs and prac-

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tices as idol worship. This paved the way for the Christian converts to disregard the indigenous ecological laws. The disregard thus saw the beginning of the steady environmental degradation in the country, which has reached unprecedented levels today. Consequently, there is the need for respect for indigenous ecological practices particularly those that can assist in the management of current ecological crisis. This paper calls for a holistic approach to addressing the current environmental problems confronting Ghanaians in particular, and Africans in general today.

Introduction

The use of indigenous knowledge has been an essential survival element throughout human history. Studies have shown (Berkes, F., Colding, J., & Folke, C. 2000; Bombay, H., Smith, P., & Murray, A. (1997; Brook, R.K. and McLachlan, S.E. 2008) that past generations knew about environmental degradation and the need for conservation and preservation and instituted measures such as taboos and other sanctions to protect their environment. Among indigenous Ghanaian people, such measures were largely underpinned by their indigenous religion since they believe that anything that belongs to the eco-system has a strong spiritual meaning for humans. Within the framework of religious ecology/religious change and also using semi and unstructured interview guides, this paper thus examines the way Africans dealt with environmental problems before the advent of Christianity on the continent and what has been the case after its implantation. My interactions with indigenous Ghanaian people have shown that religion is one of the key bases of their local ecological practices and laws and thus, anything that affects their beliefs and practices has implications for local environmental conservation. The discussion follows

the following outline. There is a brief touch on the methods of data collection, an overview of indigenous Ghanaian worldview. This is followed by how the combined forces of colonialism and Christianity weakened indigenous ecological practices, a look at the way forward then a concluding remarks.

Methodology

The content of this paper is the result of a research in religious environmentalism over the past eight years (2008-2016). It is based on my research into how indigenous people, particularly the Akan in Ghana relate with their environment, and the challenges they face with their encounter with the combine forces of colonialism and Christianity. My key informants have been a cross-section of the local people, including community leaders (chiefs), the elderly, local religious leaders (indigenous African religion believers) who gave me their views on changes in environmental conditions and their interpretations of the changes. Qualitative methods (Holloway and Wheeler 1996, Morse 1999) have been the major methodology for the gathering of the data with particular emphasis on in-depth interviews (semi and unstructured guides), focus group discussions and participant-observation. These qualitative methods were complemented by a literature review on religion and environment/ecology.

The Indigenous Ghanaian worldview

Before discussing why some people place the current environment problem at the doorsteps of Christianity and to help one follow the arguments being advanced in this paper, the paper deems it helpful to briefly outline the worldview of the people on whom the paper is based before their encounter with colonialism and its key appendage—Christianity.

I have already underscored the fact that religion permeates the life and thought of the indigenous Ghanaians.

That is, they have a theistic worldview. But what is a worldview? Worldview is being used here to mean ‘the set of assumptions that the people hold about the universe, which informs their understanding and interpretation of the nature and scope of reality. In other words, I am talking about how the indigenous Ghanaians perceive or understand the world and their immediate environment which they share with other beings’ (Awuah-Nyamekye, 2014, 59). For the indigenous believers, the presence and influence of God, the lesser gods and the ancestors are taken for granted even when they are not mentioned directly. It is against this backdrop that we have religion pervading all spheres of their lives including their secular activities. And for their use of land, what underpins it is the belief that the land is a gift from God and their ancestors and, therefore, must be treated as a sacred entity. The influence of religion on the African is so profound that eminent scholars on African society such as Parrinder (1962, 9) and Mbiti (1969, 1) have at one point described them as ‘incurably religious’ and ‘notoriously religious’ respectively. It is, therefore, important for especially the non-African, especially the Western European and the American to understand the African in this light, else, it will be difficult for one to appreciate how indigenous Africans relate to their environment in this discussion. -

Chieftaincy is the indigenous political system of the people with the chief as the overall head of his or her community. That makes the chief the most important person in the community because his/her office has religious connotations. The chief is seen as the earth representative of the ancestors. This explains why his/her office is regulated by a lot of taboos. The laws made by the chief and his elders are deemed to have divine backing and as a result, his/her subjects are ready to abide by them. In the words of Akrong

(1991, 196), ‘ the sacred nature of kingship is based on the belief that the king’s divine status as the mediator of the divine power enables him to perform the necessary rituals capable of sustaining and protecting society from chaos’. For this reason, all the environmental laws were enforced by the chiefs and their elders. The people are ready to abide by these laws even when under no compulsion. The reason is that they strongly believe that the gods and the ancestors are omnipresent and watching their activities all the time. This worldview enabled the people to live in harmony with nature

This was the situation before the people’s encounter with colonialism and its key appendage—Christianity. From the time that colonialism and Christianity gained firm root in the country, Ghanaians and, for that matter, Africans life began to change. Both indigenous political system and their religion began to lose their influence on people during colonial rule. The details of this change and its effect on environmental conservation will soon be discussed.

Although the claim that indigenous people relate well with nature has been a subject of debate among scholars (Schoffeleers 1978; Berkes 2008; Tucker and Grim; Bauman *et al* 2011; Alley, 1998, 2002 ; Tomalin 2002; Taringa 2006; Tan 2014). There is evidence that indigenous people’s environmental models can be harnessed to play a key role in solving the environmental problems of today. This reality has been championed by many scholars such as: Schoffeleers 1978; Berkes 2008; Tucker and Grim; Bauman *et al* 2011) whose studies relate to religion and ecology. But they agree that there is the need for a thorough study of how religion relate to conservation so as to know how they will be applied today.

For instance, in their introduction in their ground breaking edited book: *Grounding Religion: A field Guide to the Study of Religion and Ecology*, Bauman *et al* (2011: 3) argue,

rightly, that: ‘If religion is to be relevant to our time, it needs to respond to the reality of environmental degradation’ (p. 3), and furthermore that ‘if faith traditions and spiritual practices are to fulfill their role as moral guides, they need to reflect on the ethical implications of these trends and to lead people of faith to more just and sustainable lives’ (p. 4). It is important to stress here that those indigenous African religio-cultural beliefs and practices have from time immemorial been providing these moral guides that today Bauman and his friends are talking about. This can be attested to by their religio-cultural beliefs and practices such as totemism, the institution of sacred grove, *sasa* (a kind of *tumi* [spirit] believed to be residing in a certain kind of flora and fauna), belief in sacred days and their general attitude towards land/earth, strange landscape and others (Awuah-Nyamekye 2014). For example, among the indigenous Ghanaians, before one cuts a tree, mines a mountain, or dams a river, or kills an animal it is important for one to placate the spirit believed to be residing in that entity (see also White 1967).

Again, scholars such as Ntiamua-Baidu 2008; Byers *et al.* 2001, Schoffeleers 1978 who have done extensive study among indigenous Africans and elsewhere across the world, clearly attest to the fact that areas where the indigenous religion is strong, the ecosystem there, particularly, flora and fauna seem to be better conserved than those areas where the influence of indigenous religion is weak.

Abayie-Boaten (1998) stresses that many traditional African societies conceive of themselves as stewards of the environment, with social and moral obligations to manage and conserve it for posterity (see Attfield, 2010; Mawere, 2014). Writing in support of this view, Agboro (2008) notes that majority of Africans conceive humans and their environment to be ‘two inseparable entities that cannot be divorced

from each other'. Ontologically, traditional African people believe that human beings did not just happen to be in this world, they were designed to live in the world in relation to their environment(s). What this implies is that environmental consciousness is embedded in the traditional African worldview (Awuah-Nyamekye, 2009. Opoku-Ankomah *et al.* (2010), observe that culturally acceptable environmental management among Africans emanates from social organisation that is permeated by spirituality and a reverence for ancestors. This can be argued to be the foundation of African environmental ethics. As has earlier on been pointed out, indigenous ways of protecting and conserving the environment suffered greatly when Christianity took the centre stage in the Ghana's and, for that matter, Africa's religious landscape.

How the combined forces of colonialism and Christianity weakened indigenous conservation practices in Ghana

As has already been outlined, the chiefs became the fulcrum of activities in the pre-colonial Ghanaian society, particularly in the areas of governance, religion and the general weal of the community including ensuring environmental sanity. When the whole of Ghana came under the reign of the British imperial power, steps were taken to weaken the power of the chiefs over their subjects. Although the British imperial power adopted what became known as *indirect rule*—where the people were ruled through the chiefs, this can best be described as sham. This is because it was a subtle way to hide their real intentions. The real power of the chiefs over their subjects was taken away. For instance, the governors introduced a series of laws which included: *Native Jurisdiction Ordinances*, *Native Administrative Ordinance*, *Native Authority Ordinance* and they were all aimed at reducing the authorities of the traditional rulers. The *Native Authority Ordinance* for instance, enabled a Native Authority to be appointed by the government. However,

under the law, the decisions of the Native Authority could be reviewed or even set aside by the governor (Buah 1999; see Awuah-Nyamekye 2014).

In the religious field, soon after its arrival, Christianity began a sustained onslaught against indigenous African religio-cultural beliefs and practices. Indigenous African religion was not only seen as false, uncivilised behaviour, but was demonised and was described in pejorative terms such as fetishism, paganism, polytheism, heathenism, and many others. This posture was maintained where ever Christianity took roots in Africa. In many places, some overzealous Christian converts saw even the chieftaincy institution as idol worship due to the role religion plays in it. In many places throughout the country, some Christians openly challenged the authority of their chiefs.

An interlocutor reacted to this attitude thus:

Eneemafo [the youth of today who have adopted Christianity] do not regard our tradition anymore. When *Kwasibroni* (the Whiteman) came with their Bible, all our gods were rendered ineffective. They said our gods were false gods. Our people now challenge the tradition with impunity. The youth do not respect the elderly. They see our tradition as old fashioned (*ɔpanyin* Kyere Kwame, personal communication, 6 November 2011, see Awuah-Nyamekye 2014).

A ninety year-old woman lamented on the current situation in the following words:

Many years ago --when a majority of us were attached to the religion of our forefathers--we did not have problems at all with the environment. There was plenty of rainfall for our crops and plenty of big trees. Fresh air was in abundance. But

now, the rainfall pattern has changed drastically. The rains do not come at the time that they are expected and when they come, they do not last as they used to. The worst of this is the excessive heat we are experiencing which has resulted in crop failure and strange diseases. This change in the weather has even affected our rivers. Those that used to be perennial are now seasonal. I blame this on the disrespectfulness that has characterised our society today. *Eneemafoɔ* are difficult to control. They have no respect for our customs and tradition. This started when *Kwasibroni* (the Whiteman) brought his school and religion to us. This has seriously affected the overall weal of our environment (*Maame Ackoma*, personal communication, 5 October 2011; see Awuah-Nyamekye 2014).

The effects of Christianity on African Traditional Religion and Culture have been expressed by Nukunya in the following words:

In order to understand the effects of Christianity on African culture, it is necessary to realise that traditional institutions never existed or functioned separately like discrete entities but dovetailed into one another. Religion for instance never operated independently of the kinship structure and the social control and vice versa. Any impingement on the religious beliefs, practices and organisations was, therefore, bound to affect not only that aspect of social life but also other elements of it. Soon after its arrival, Christianity began to attack African culture and belief systems. Some of the major targets of the missionary assault include: ancestor veneration, divination, rites of passage procedures and ceremonies of marriage. In attacking these beliefs and practices, the missionaries were not striking at anything but the very roots of the Africans' culture (Nukunya 1986: 87).

For instance, as has been noted already, prior to the introduction of Christianity in Ghana in 1482, traditional

ecological practices were hugely underpinned by the indigenous religion, but with advent of the missionaries and later African Christians, these beliefs and practices came to be viewed as idol worship. Consequently, many of the indigenous ways of conserving nature were bastardised. In fact, Christians disregarded the indigenous ecological laws (taboos and sanctions) for they saw them as encouraging idol worship. This weakened indigenous African religion and its influence on the people just as it had done to the power of the chiefs to enforce environmental laws. Therefore, places, animals and other entities such as rivers viewed as sacred entities lost their sacrosanctity. It is now a common phenomenon to find churches built in areas marked as sacred groves. Totemic plants and animals have become victims. Before the Christianity era, rivers were believed to be deities. No one dared to even live to close to a river. But the Christian religion came to condemn all these beliefs. Today, one finds houses built even in the river beds because Christianity has made the people to believe that the belief in rivers having deities is a false one. The result is the perennial floods in our cities and towns whenever, there is a heavy down pour.

But, one important fact must be underscored here, and it is this, that, my interaction with my key informants, however, did not suggest that Christianity is an anti-ecological conservation religion.

What, however, stands out clearly among my interlocutors is the Christians' attitude towards African indigenous religion, which is, the debasing of the religion. I have pointed out earlier, indigenous constitutes a major live-wire that ensures the enforcement of their indigenous ecological conservation practices., therefore according to them, the damnation of their religion by Christians paved way for the wanton destruction of the environment today in Gha-

na and, for that matter, many parts of sub-Saharan Africa. Their position reflects what Lynn White pointed out in 1967 that: “By destroying pagan animism, Christianity made it possible to exploit nature in a mood of indifference to the feelings of natural objects” (White 1967). Although some scholars such as Johnson and Butigan, 1984; Harrison, 1999; Attfield 1983, 2010) disagreed with White’s theory. Some even such as Alley, 1998, 2002,; Taringa 2006; Tomalin 2002) have questioned the capacity of indigenous religion to handle environmental issues efficiently. It must be said that in spite of this counter claim, the fact still remains that it was after the publication of the Rachel Carson’s *Silent Spring*, in 1962 and later White’s thesis that ‘dominion’ in Genesis 1: 28 (... subdue it and have dominion over...) came to be understood as implying ‘stewardship’ see Mensah, 2012: 31). By this, the paper is not saying that Christianity is an anti conservationist religion because there are passages in the Bible that support conservation of nature. Calvin De Witt an evangelical theologian cum zoologist, for instance, argues that “his faith tradition [Christianity] has the resources necessary to constructively respond to the carelessness and inattention that have led to ecological devastation... [for him] the Bible contains divinely inspired wisdom about creation, and that if we pay attention to this text we can learn to relate to other creatures as God intends” (De Witt 2011:59).] He even describes the current environmental degradation as ‘blasphemous’ (De Witt 2011:60).

Another important finding that must be underscored is the fact that in spite of the inroads that Christianity has made in Ghana, the influence of the indigenous religion has not waned completely. It continues to influence the life of some people, particularly, those in the rural communities. This explains why the ecosystems in the rural areas look

better conserved than in those in the urban areas. Again, it is common phenomenon in Ghana, and elsewhere in Africa for many Christians to turn to indigenous religious beliefs and practices when hit with affliction or chronic and terminal diseases. This attitude is what I refer to as hybridity (Awuah-Nyamekye 2014). This fact seems to contradict the argument of the paper---Christianity being responsible for the current environmental woes in Ghana. But, paradoxically that is the case, and many studies carried out by scholars such as Gyekye 1996; Mbiti and Burleson 1986; and Shorter, 1975: 7 among Ghanaians and elsewhere in Africa confirm this. Many of my interlocutors mentioned that they often meet people who claim to be Christians at traditional African priests' shrines soliciting assistance in one way or the other. It is, however, important to stress that this fact does not negate the argument of the paper because the effect of Christianity, most especially its condemnation of indigenous African religion, has been phenomenal on the way of life of the people. What is being emphasised at this point is that this ambivalent nature of Ghanaians has implications for environmental conservation in Ghana today.

The way Forward

I have pointed out that in spite of the major inroad Christianity has made in Ghana, many people in the rural communities still hold on to the indigenous religion and even those who claimed to be Christians find it difficult to do away completely with their indigenous worldview, particularly in matters of religion. Mbiti and Burleson (1986: 12) for instance, observed that: 'Africans come out of African religion but they don't take off their traditional religiosity. They come as they are. They come as people whose worldview is shaped according to African religion'. In line with this view, Gyekye (1996: 4) points out that 'to be born into African society is

to be born into a culture that is intensely and pervasively religious and that means, and requires, participating in the religious beliefs and rituals of the community.’ So Aylward Shorter, when he pointed out that the African Christian does away with ‘remarkably little of his former non- Christian outlook.’ (1975: 7).

The implication of the above is that religion cannot be ignored when designing any serious environmental conservation policy as it has been an acceptable fact that religious beliefs and practices play a vital role in believers’ conduct, and particularly when there is evidence that the scientific means of conserving nature alone have not been adequate. This means there is the need for a support. This support, in the view of this paper, can be tapped from the local people. That is, from their indigenous ways of managing environmental problems.

Conclusion

The foregoing has unearthed the consequences of the combined efforts of colonialism and Christianity on indigenous Ghanaian ways of managing their environmental problems. Although the indigenous religion has shown some level of resilience to the effects it has suffered from colonialism and Christianity, yet, its effectiveness in handling environmental issues of today is problematic. However, it is also true that this does not mean it can be ignored in the equation, particularly where its influence continues to hold sway on some of the people and again, the modern or scientific ways of managing the environmental problems in Ghana and across the globe are still not adequate.

What, therefore, needs to be done is to engage in a rigorous study of these local environment knowledge system which the people strongly believed has religious underpin-

nings with the view to identifying those that are relevant today and integrate them into those of science in order to have a holistic approach to the current environmental problems in Ghana in particular, and Africa in general.

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